

Sustainable

Community
Governed

Cost
Recovery

Open
Infrastructure

Budget
Modeling

**OAEBUDT
Sustainability and
Budget Model
Development
Report**

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Executive Summary

Between 2023 and 2025, a sustainable business model was developed to project costs and revenue generation for the operation of a minimum viable data space and its coordinating office. A draft fee model was produced based on a comparative analysis of membership models of scholarly communications infrastructures, stakeholder feedback, and cash flow data from a Data Space as a Service (DSaaS) pilot focused on scholarly impact metric data connectors.

A three-year budgetary model for data space coordination was developed with funding targets to guide the infrastructure's next stage of development and service launch. Fundraising campaign pilots in 2024 and 2025 examined market receptivity and capacity to provide funds for operational cash flow and reserves to support the open, community-governed infrastructure. The costs of providing minimum viable core services (*i.e.*, Cost of Goods Sold – COGS) and the minimum number of paying organizational participants to break even were determined.

Staffing models at varying levels of capacity set operational reserve targets; yet, fundraising pilots did not reach any threshold that could support the launch of a multi-year data space offering that could guarantee access to an active minimum viable data space with a usage data connector service.

Case studies of pilot OAEBUDT DSaaS participants signaled that value of data space participation depended on a critical mass of DSaaS participants committing to incorporating the DSaaS into existing API workflows. Additional data connector “use cases” would be needed to sustain a DSaaS across scholarly communications stakeholders. The OAEBUDT brand and governance was thus sunset to make way for a broader global scholarly communications data space network to continue this work.

This report documents the OAEBUDT DSaaS costs, revenue generation options, and budgetary model for future scholarly communications data space development.

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Background

Sustainability Modeling for a Data Space focused on an e-Book Usage Data Connector

The Open Access eBook Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT) effort originated to address challenges related to the aggregation and benchmarking of openly licensed book impact metrics across enterprises and regulatory frameworks. In open science, distributed, decentralized usage of humanities and social science e-books is the norm. Prior work with book content funders, publishers, distributors, and analytics services discovered data sharing barriers to high-quality, holistic multi-platform analytics.ⁱ Some entities could not release granular or real-time data for ingest or copying into a third-party data broker or processor due to regulatory or privacy issues, and/or perceived risk. To resolve this issue, in 2023 the OAEBUDT effort began to develop governance mechanisms for an International Data Spaceⁱⁱ that could enable direct data connectors that make sovereign data flows observable and controllable by the organizations that generate and make usage data dynamically available per licensing agreements.

Prior to data space development, research determined stakeholders, value propositions, user requirements, potential solutions, market dynamics, and pricing considerations for OA book usage data exchange (Table 1). Key factors surfaced to inform sustainability modeling for an International Data Spaceⁱⁱⁱ (IDS) for OA book usage.

- 1) Standards and infrastructures must evolve to meet demand for advanced contextual analytics related to scholarship impact data with more granular, timely, and interoperable data beyond static aggregate reports. Trust in the underlying data was paramount.
- 2) Growing awareness of the potential risks and harms associated with open publication of usage data for unrestricted use in the public domain shifted usage data provision conversations from “fully open publication” to “as open as possible, but as controlled as necessary” to support reader privacy, ethical data use, and legal obligations. Agentic workflows increased stakeholder desire for solutions.
- 3) Increased awareness of data stewardship and the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance^{iv}, increased demand for scalable, responsive data governance solutions for data intermediation among organizations.
- 4) Emerging European data regulations aimed at controlling the sharing and use of data as it is transferred across national boundaries would influence centralized data brokerage platforms, i.e., “harvest or ingest to monetize” data products and services. Specifically, regulations related to the controlled sharing and use of public and commercial data for the common good, like the Data Governance Act, could directly impact the ability of a data brokerage or aggregator service to harvest, link, and provide access to other organizations’ data while also providing value-added analytics or reporting services tied to such data. Hence, organizations that provide cross-organization reporting and analytics services may face future regulatory requirements if also positioned as neutral data brokers, marketplaces, or other types of data intermediaries.

Stakeholders involved in OAEBUDT research discovered the industry-agnostic, interoperable International Data Space model^v and related emerging ISO/IEC standards such as ISO/IEC FDIS 20151-1^{vi} (defining Data space Concepts and characteristics), ISO/IEC DIS 26450 (defining the Eclipse Data Space Protocol^{vii}, aka DSP) and ISO/IEC DIS 26451 (defining the Decentralized Claims Protocol, aka DCP)). Anticipating that public-to-private data intermediation will be impacted by European regulation^{viii}, stakeholders considered how data space adoption could enforce and automate “as controlled as necessary” protocol-level data sharing policy across the scholarly communications supply chain. Given how disruptive and unfamiliar this decentralized approach was in the context of repositories, centralized data commons, and other collectives acting as centralized data brokers, awareness raising was paramount. Stakeholders did not understand how data spaces transform real-time observability, transparency, and policy control over downstream data access and use.

Table 1: Foundational Research that Informed OAEBUDT-IDS Sustainability Modeling

Topic	Key Outputs	Year
Open Science Usage Data		
Shared challenges related to usage data analytics	White Papers ^{ix, x}	2018, 2019
Usage data supply-chain for OA books	Report ^{xi} , Data-flow Diagrams ^{xii}	2021
Guiding principles for OA book usage data services	Principles ^{xiii}	2021
Usage data applications by stakeholder	Report ^{xiv} , Value Propositions Diagram ^{xv}	2022
Usage data supply-chains for open journals and data	Report, Data-flow Diagrams ^{xvi}	2024
International Data Space Operations		
International Data Spaces	Design Principles ^{xvii} , Reference Architecture Model ^{xviii} , Rulebook ^{xix}	2019, 2021 and subsequent
Scholarly Communication Open Infrastructures		
Environmental scan	Report ^{xx}	2021
Business modeling for usage data exchange	Report ^{xxi} , Business Model Canvas ^{xxii}	2021
Legal analysis	Legal Agenda ^{xxiii}	2021
Technical gap analysis of data space model against existing open infrastructures	Report ^{xxiv}	2024
OA Book Usage Data Space Pilot		
OA book usage data connector and data space community participation requirements	OAEBUDT Participant Rulebook ^{xxv}	2024
OAEBUDT Data Space MVP Proof of Concept	Open-Source Software ^{xxvi} , Documentation ^{xxvii} , Technical Roadmap ^{xxviii}	2025
OA Usage Data Connector Pilot Case Studies	Report ^{xxix}	2025
MVP Data Space Return on Investment Analysis	Report ^{xxx}	2025

Mid-2021, the Mellon Foundation funded the *Developing a Pilot Data Trust for Open Access eBook Usage* project to develop governance mechanisms for the usage data focused data space. As a supply-chain wide neutral community-governed infrastructure, the data space would allow organizations to join and configure direct data connectors to automate licensing compliance and observe downstream usage of shared usage data. From 2024-2025, the OAEBUDT data space staff, board, and fiscal host piloted a data space coordinating office to centralize administrative functions including governance support, agreement processing, fundraising, accounting, communications, outreach, and technical dataspace-as-a-service (DSaaS) provider coordination. Costs encountered by the coordinating office were captured to inform budgetary model development.

A proof of concept, minimum viable data space was built and piloted in 2025, refining the coordination cost model for a decentralized, community-governed and supported data space.

EU and US Open Access Book Publishing Markets: 2023-to-2026

Since 2018, the European scholarly communications market navigated Plan S while the US market responded to the 2022 “Nelson Memo”. Despite these market drivers towards open science, in 2023 the 2.2 Billion dollar global open science publishing market showed indications of slowing.^{xxxi} The relatively small budgets of OA publisher service providers came into focus, with efforts like the DARIAH project finding a “large majority” of those operating in the European Research Area surviving on 50,000/year, with financial resources and relationship continuity challenging sustainability.^{xxxii}

Between 2022 and 2025, funding capacity for open publishing services in the American scholarly communications market shifted significantly. Ithaka S&R’s 2025 Library Survey^{xxxiii} surfaced how the percentage of library respondents

prioritizing open investments or subscriptions fell from 41% to 22%. In anticipation of reduced library budgets, 84% cited a reduction in spending on subscriptions while 33% cited plans to reduce association memberships. This shift significantly impacted the OAEBUDT model, which was developing to meet the needs of open publishers, platforms, and service providers. As US libraries were considering the reduction of operational costs by renegotiating vendor contracts (87%), leveraging consortia (64%), or otherwise partnering to share costs (59%), strategies oriented around direct library payments had to adjust to prioritize consortium partnership.^{xxxiv} The appetite for early stage innovation support shifted; clear ROI was necessary in this time of conservative, constraining publisher and platform budgets.

The OAEBUDT data space developed its sustainable budget model during these shifts. From 2023-2025 stakeholders in workshops, focus groups, conference sessions, and advisory bodies guided and informed iterative model development.

Modeling for Extensibility - Adjusting to a Broader Mission and Scope

The initial OA book usage focus of data space development attracted a small set of collaborative monograph stakeholders wanting to simplify the aggregation and benchmarking of distributed book usage data. Yet, infrastructure governance was developed to be extensible, with policies and technology that could support other types of real-time, granular sensitive data intermediation across decentralized organizations.

Project advisors and the elected OAEBUDT governance kept in mind a data space’s potential to transform other types of cross-platform real-time operational data sharing in scholarly communications, a concept referred to as extensibility. Thus, OAEBUDT’s governance guided the development of a data space coordinating office, its [guiding principles](#), mission, vision, and the common rules it would enforce across the data space’s network of organizational participants.

Table 2: Principle Documents that Informed OAEBUDT-IDS Sustainability Modeling

Guiding Document	DOI
Guiding Principles for OA Book Usage Data Services	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5842413
Principles of Open Infrastructure	https://doi.org/10.24343/C34W2H
Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust - International Data Space (OAEBUDT-IDS)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11163157
International Data Spaces Association Rulebook (defining minimum requirements for data space structure and governance)	https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDSA-Rulebook
International Data Spaces Association Reference Architecture Model (defining minimum requirements for technical data space architecture)	https://kb.internationaldataspaces.org/external/ram/ For more information see: https://internationaldataspaces.org/ram-5-within-idsas-document-landscape/

Sustainability modeling explored ways to recover the cost of coordinating, governing, and centrally administering shared data space infrastructure and protocols across decentralized, sovereign organizations that independently managed their data connectors. In the first two years of modeling, the assumption was that the data space would exclusively focus on supporting a single data connector for open scholarship usage and impact metrics. This assumption proved to be unsustainable, as a broader set of stakeholders and use cases were determined to be necessary to support a data space and scholarly communications at scale.

To sustain data space coordination on annual participant payments, a critical mass of participants or subsidies would be required during the early years of operation. Data collected on revenue generation, membership benefits and pricing, and centralized operation costs informed this finding. Staffing scenarios at low, medium, and high levels of support were analyzed against the cost of operating the usage data connector. Results prompted governance to formally extend the mission, vision, and brand from OAEBUDT to a broader “Trusted Scholarly Communications Data

Space” in late 2025. The OAEBUDT board dissolved in April 2026 so that a new governance body connected to a broader data space participant network and set of use cases could emerge.

This report summarizes the findings related to a sustainable budget, staffing, and growth model for a data space focused on granular, controlled open scholarship usage and impact related data intermediation so they can be extended by the book, publishing, open science, and scholarly communications industries.

Business Model Canvas

Preliminary Model - 2021

In 2021, just as the OAEBUDT team discovered data spaces, More Brains LLC produced an initial Business Model Canvas (BMC) for a usage data exchange network^{xxxv}. This work was completed prior to the development of the OAEBUDT governance model, participant rulebook, and data space infrastructure, with limited knowledge of the costs associated with implementing a coordinating office for an International Data Space (IDS). This preliminary model had multiple assumptions that did not align with emerging data space protocols and business models.

- Assumption: The Academic Observatory code base developed by COKI would be sufficient to handle data intermediation for OA book usage. *Finding: data ingest raised data provider concerns that could not be addressed by legal contracts alone; instead, granular sensitive data was not shared.*
- Assumption: Prominent value propositions included data cleaning and normalization. *Finding: Without the policy-based controls and logging of data transfer or access made possible by a data space's data connectors, such activities could not mitigate the risks associated with third party copies of sensitive data, even though they could be offered in a data connector and generate value.*
- Assumption: A singular platform API would be the channel to adoption. *Finding: This approach did not clearly align with the data space standards for decentralized sovereign data intermediation across platforms.*

DataSpace-as-a-Service Model - 2023

Two years later, a revised BMC for an OAEBUDT Data Space-as-a-Service (DSaaS) was created based on emerging DSaaS administration costs and revenue generation categories.^{xxxvi} This BMC focused on a data connector service for scholarly communications organizations to configure and observe and/or discover and audit, direct machine-actionable data pipelines for specific data sharing and use agreements. Presented to OA book stakeholders in focus groups and workshops from November 2023 to March 2024, the revised BMC included:

- The types of organizations that could connect to a data space as data providers, data recipients, and infrastructure partners
- The activities provided by an OAEBUDT data space coordinating office
- The resources required to provide such services in a DSaaS
- Key value propositions and initial user segments
- Key relationships and outreach channels for service delivery
- Cost categories and cost-recovery mechanisms

Figure 1: Representation of Data Space Governance and Technology on Top of Existing Data Flows

Created pre-technical pilot, the revised 2023 BMC incorporated the following board developed guiding principles^{xxxvii}:

- The data space would operate as community-governed open infrastructure in line with the Principles for Open Infrastructure, with diverse revenue streams and an operational reserve
- Trust issue resolution and intra-network standardization of required metadata disclosures were necessary to improve data quality and address gamification across the DSaaS participant network. Direct governance by DSaaS users was necessary.
- Data space development would align with the global standards in the IDSA Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM)^{xxxviii} and IDSA Rulebook^{xxxix} to provide a certifiable, decentralized, cloud-based data intermediation service compliant with ISO 20151 and ISO 26451.
- Source code and documentation would be open infrastructure; but the openness of the data transiting the data space would be dictated and managed directly by the upstream organizations that own and/or contractually provide data via the data space. No data would be centrally stored or ingested in a common repository for data brokerage or secondary use.
- Technical and governance development would support future extensibility beyond an OA book usage data connector.

BMC assumptions were tested from 2024-2025 as the proof-of-concept data space was developed^{xi}, documented^{xii}, and piloted^{xiii} with a data connector to support the use case of OA book usage data exchange and aggregation. As the cloud-based data space infrastructure shared attributes with other types of Software-as-a-Service (SaaS), OAEBUDT Finance and Fundraising Committee members reviewed sustainability models for SaaS for insights. To identify the COGS (Cost of Goods Sold, i.e., cost of provisioning the data connector service in a data space), care was taken to separate the cost of technical DSaaS service provisioning from the expenses associated with data space participant network coordination and governance facilitation.

Figure 2: 2023 Business Model Canvas for the OAEBUDT Data Space

Data Space Costs

Data space costs were identified for the provision of the DSaaS technology stack, the coordination of data space participants, service providers, and governance. While costs are described below, prices should be viewed with caution given recent variability in technical hardware and cloud computing expenses due to market adjustments to AI-driven demand.

DSaaS Technology Stack and Services

To bring a data space to market with minimum knowledge, OAEBUDT sought out experts who were developing, maintaining, and standardizing other open-source industrial data spaces. Request for Proposal (RFP)^{xliii} responses from multiple expert firms surfaced initial build and ongoing hyperscale cloud computing costs associated with sustaining a DataSpace-as-a-Service (DSaaS). While the cloud infrastructure could be hosted within any neutral organization with High Performance Computing (HPC) capacity, the upskilling cost for developer training on data space protocols fell outside the scope of project resources. Technical costs were identified for centralized infrastructure, isolated data connectors, and customer support. Pricing models differed across DSaaS proposals and proposal contents were proprietary. Estimates informed by proposals were incorporated into the budget model.

Central Infrastructure for User Credentialing, Data Connector Discovery, and Policy Clearing

Dynamically scalable, containerized cloud infrastructure is necessary for a DSaaS to sustainably ensure that authorized parties (or agents) have logged access to only the data connectors they are authorized to view, access, and use. A cloud computing contract, with variable cost based on number of data space participants and data connector complexity, is required to provide infrastructure for the coordinating office to manage: 1) data space

participant profile issuance, 2) dynamic licensed access logging, 3) data connector discovery, and 4) issue reporting and resolution. A trusted organization could host these central DSaaS functions on leased or owned cloud infrastructure. For the OAEBUDT proof of concept pilot, OPERAS contracted with DSaaS provider Think-IT to ensure compliance with emerging data space and decentralized claims protocols.

Costs for centralized functions are realized once a DSaaS is active, regardless of whether a participant is actively using the infrastructure. Step increases in this cost category are expected as the number of data space participants and/or number of data connectors increases within a data space. To tightly control costs during the minimum viable OAEBUDT DSaaS pilot, verified credentialing was manually configured and the development of a transaction clearinghouse and user interfaces for connector discovery and reporting were postponed.^{xiv} A fully functioning DSaaS would need to implement such centralized data space administration functions to handle activity initiated autonomously by data providers, data consumers, or their agents.

Decentralized Data Connectors

Large enterprises participating in operational data spaces often host and maintain their own cloud-based “data connector” policy gateways to directly manage licensed data use via API extensions through the DSaaS.

Small to medium enterprises often lack the human and cloud resources to host and manage their own data connector interfaces.^{xiv} In open publishing, scholar-led, university press, and independent publishers are examples of participants that may require a hosted data connector solution to participate in a data space.

To control costs and simplify the pilot partner experience, a “Hosted Data Connector” service was provisioned by Think-IT for OAEBUDT DSaaS pilot participants. Participants connected their content (i.e., data endpoints) to the hosted data connectors maintained by Think-IT. While a DSaaS coordinating office could theoretically provide this hosted data connector service to lesser resourced organizations, the neutrality operating principle makes it preferential to instead partner with service providers that comply with the DSaaS Participant Rulebook. By neutrally advertising partner hosted data connector services, a coordinating office can scale effectively, avoid perceived conflicts of interest, and support decentralized innovation. Savvy data processors could decide to offer such hosted data connectors as a service to position as a gateway to the scholarly communications data space.

Documentation and Support

A DSaaS must provide technical support to coordinating office staff, data space participants, and service partners. Direct support and documentation effort must be budgeted, with scalable costs associated with the number of organizational participants in the data space and length of each participant’s engagement with the DSaaS. First year onboarding participants are expected to require more support than integrated, operational participants.

Table 3: Technical Costs Associated with Dataspace-as-a-Service Provision

Dataspace-as-a-Service Provision (Technology) (Estimated at X Euro/year for the MVP OAEBUDT DSaaS)		
Functional Category	Description	Related Line Items
Technical Service Contract with Dataspace-as-a-Service Provider	Hosting, maintenance, and baseline support, for DSaaS verified identity service, secrets manager, data connector discovery service, and transaction clearinghouse	Consultant Contract / Retainer Fee
Hosted Data Connector	For smaller or less technically sophisticated organizations unable to create or host their own enterprise’s virtual data connectors	Consultant Contract / Retainer Fee
Documentation and Customer Support	Technical support for use-case development and documentation, user and system administrator documentation, onboarding support, participant training, and customer support	Consultant Contract / Retainer Fee

The technical pilot illuminated variable, fixed, and one-time costs associated with DSaaS hosting and technical support. Cost estimates provided a baseline for planning, recognizing that cloud compute costs could be reduced if DSaaS connectors and identity management functions were available as subsidized public infrastructure on national grids or national research and education networks.

Table 4: Sample Technical DSaaS Costs in Euro Rounded to the nearest 1000

Contracted DSaaS Service	Annual Fixed Costs	Variable Costs
Hosted Data Connector (e.g. Usage Data Connector)		7000 per connector
Four managed XL cloud clusters (e.g. AWS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dev (for onboarding) 	5000	
XL AWS EC2 for coordinating office rules processing / routing	1000	
Onboarding support for participants (5 days of technical time)		2,000 per opt-in participant

As AI and data centers increase energy prices and computing demand, such costs are likely to increase.

Data Space Coordinating Office

Administrative Support

A centralized data space coordinating office facilitates and provides administrative support for community-led governance, contract management, issue resolution, and shared resource development. Administrative functions span fiscal and staff administration, marketing and communications, facilitation, and vendor management. Specialized expertise in international contracts, global data transfer and payroll regulation should be accessible based on the operational footprint of data space participants and service provider partners. During the OAEBUDT DSaaS pilot, such functions were managed across staff, contractors and OPERAS acting as fiscal administrative host of the data space’s coordinating office.

Legal Consultation

Costs associated with investigation and remediation are expected to support participant-reported data quality issues following processes defined in the OAEBUDT DSaaS Rulebook. Once operational, a DSaaS supports supply chain workflows where data connector disconnection can negatively impact downstream data recipient products and services and the data provider’s reputation. Risk exposure must be carefully managed through standard contractual clauses, participation agreements, and operating policies. A retainer for potential legal assistance should be budgeted to ensure capacity to address issues and advise as necessary.

International Payroll and Compliance

Human resources to support staffed coordinating office roles could be administered by a Professional Employer Organization, fiscal-host, or other community-based consortia that neutrally administers global open infrastructures. Such partnerships streamline multi-country regulatory compliance, taxation, and payments for full-time or contract-based roles. Care must be taken to ensure alignment between the DSaaS participant community and the coordinating office host to ensure capacity, alignment, and neutrality can be maintained for trusted operations and coordination.^{xlvi}

SLA-Compliant Staff Capacity

A data space coordinating office must meet its obligations in the OAEBUDT rulebook and service level agreements for data space uptime and issue resolution response. Staffing scalability and responsiveness must be reflected in the cost model to ensure obligations and expectations can be met.

Marketing, Outreach, and Communications

Communications infrastructure and travel support are necessary for community engagement and data space participant network growth. While some fiscal hosts provide communications software and services, DSaaS coordinating office staff time is necessary for messaging strategy, alignment and direct meetings with participants.

Industrial Ecosystem Engagement

Associations can facilitate ecosystem level change and data space adoption; yet, membership dues are necessary for access to such strategic networks. During the OAEBUDT project, US-based coordinating office staff leveraged domestic membership in multiple associations including the Coalition for Networked Information (CNI), the Society for Scholarly Publishing (SSP), and the National Information Standards Organization (NISO), and participation in the global COUNTER Metrics, Research Data Alliance (RDA), and International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) communities.

Research and Development

Since the OAEBUDT DSaaS was able to leverage open-source code developed in other data spaces, such as the Eclipse Data Connectors, development rapidly progressed to a Technical Readiness Level^{xlvii} of 7. The proof of concept, minimum viable data space was successfully built and piloted with an OA usage data connector. Since a single usage focused connector is not sufficient to sustain the data space, further research and development is needed to document additional valuable direct data connectors in scholarly communications. Full data space functionality must be developed to incorporate features omitted from the MVP due to the proof of concept's budget and time constraints. Central technical coordination is necessary to maintain knowledge in the coordinating office and manage strategic directions for the technical DSaaS stack. Finally, to support internationalization non-English character interface development should be planned to support global participants.

Scholarly Communications Data space Research and Development (Next Stage)			
Functional Category	Description	Related Line Items	Estimate
Data space Research and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> License policy checks via DSaaS transaction clearinghouse DSaaS user interfaces Coordinating Office Administration interface Internationalization of interfaces Additional data connector use-cases 	Project-based Contracts	Varies by scope, provider
Technical Development and Roadmap Management			
Staffing	Human resources for technical support and contracted service coordination, including management of public facing roadmap.	Salaries and Wages for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technical Director, Technical Community Engagement Coordinator(s) 	Varies by salary scale and country basis
Staff Benefits and Payroll Processing	Compensation benefits and insurance for technical staff based on location of employment; including global payroll processing fees	Insurance, e.g., Health, Dental, Life, Unemployment, Leave Balances: e.g., Vacation and Sick Leave, Payroll Processing Fees	~30% of pay

Indirect Costs

In total, 30% of program costs should be budgeted to cover indirect charges related to fiscal sponsorship, cross-border financial administration, and insurance policies.

Fiscal Sponsorship

During the OAEBUDT DSaaS pilot, an MOU between the OAEBUDT Board of Trustees and OPERAS-EU allowed OPERAS-EU to act as a fiscal and legal administrative host for the DSaaS coordinating office. The administration of participant agreement contracts, payments and invoicing, and vendor services was provided for a standard “fiscal hosting” rate. During the search for a fiscal host, overhead rates surfaced ranging from 10-50% of direct charges. The budget model initially reflected a 10% overhead rate from the pilot fiscal host MOU, although a modest increase to 15% is recommended given the range.

Global cross-border operational costs

Foreign exchange fluctuations resulted in account balance sheet credits/debits during the DSaaS pilot when currency was held other than the primary currency of the fiscal host. Funds held in US Dollars in Belgium had to be accounted for in Euro, with a valuation conversion rate calculated at the end of the fiscal year. Fiscal accounting captures this gain/loss on a fund balance sheet; thus, funds should be budgeted if multi-country currencies are held for conversion at a future date. Alternatively, the funds received can be immediately exchanged into destination currency, or participants can be charged in the fiscal host’s currency. 5% of program costs is recommended to buffer foreign currency exchange impacts if multiple currency accounts are managed.

Organizational Insurance

Insurance coverage may be required by a fiscal host to manage financial risk associated with operations and human resources, such as backfilling positions during covered family or medical leave. 15% of program costs is recommended for such insurance.

Table 5: Coordination Costs Associated with DataSpace-as-a-Service Network

DataSpace Coordinating Office Administration Expenses ~450k Euro/year + 30% overhead			
Functional Category	Description	Related Line Items	Annual Estimate
Program Costs			
Staffing	Human resources for global governance facilitation, communications and outreach, partnership development, service coordination, participant support, and breach of participation agreement issue investigation and remediation	Salaries and Wages for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Managing Director Community Engagement Coordinator(s) 	300,000
Staff Benefits and Payroll Processing	Compensation benefits and insurances for staff that may or may not be required based on location of employment; Including fees associated with using a global payroll processor to support distributed staffing HR administration	Insurance, e.g., Health, Dental, Life, Unemployment, Leave Balances: e.g., Vacation and Sick Leave, Payroll Processing Fees	~30% of staffing salaries and wages
Legal Support	Support for global data transfer advice, international contracting, and compliance support	Consultant Contract / Retainer Fee	25,000
Travel	Travel support for global communications, outreach, and relationship management	Airfare Ground Transportation Meals and Incidental Expenses Conference Registration Fees Visa Application Fees	25,000
Equipment & Supplies	For staff and governance body productivity, including back-office software licenses, website hosting, file repository, staff hardware	Computer hardware for staff SaaS such as: Microsoft 360, Google Workspace, Canva, Zoom	10,000
Other	Professional association memberships to support interoperability and alignment	E.g., IDSA membership fee, SSP membership fee, COUNTER membership fee	5,000
Indirect Costs			
Fiscal Sponsorship	Financial, technical, human resource, and accounting administration for network membership and service coordination	Fiscal Sponsorship Fee	15% of total program costs
Cross-border operational costs and foreign exchange fluctuation	Costs associated with the rise/fall of currencies when payments are made/received across the global network's currencies	Indirect Costs	10% of total program costs
Insurance	To manage organizational risk: e.g., General Liability, D&O, Cyber	Insurance Policy	5% of total program costs

Data Space Participant Costs

Organizations joining the data space and configuring a usage data connector in the OAEBUDT pilot spent 12 to 80 hours across onboarding, configuration, professional development, and data governance activities. Lower numbers focused primarily on documentation review and API configuration while higher numbers were inclusive of organizational change management across planning meetings, legal review, and development time.^{xlviii}

Preparation | Cybersecurity, Data Governance, Professional Development

Organizations directly connecting to a DSaaS must meet high levels of cybersecurity to interconnect without introducing risk to the entire data space participant network. Strong data governance with documentation is also required to configure organizational data connectors and disclose provenance and licensing terms per the DSaaS participant rulebook. Organizations may need to address internal processes and policy prior to directly connecting endpoints to a DSaaS. Technical debt and organizational change may also be necessary to adjust workflows so API connections route through the DSaaS. As “data spaces” are emergent in scholarly communications, professional development may be required to support developer and data professional learning. This is crucial as the data space protocol differs substantially from the current practice of centralized data repositories that broker, harvest, and ingest data without automated policy gateways or logging.

Onboarding

Data connector configuration is straightforward when data governance and licensing information is current and available for a data endpoint. Time may be necessary to: 1) review the DSaaS Participant Rulebook, 2) to understand how data connectors functions, and 3) review vocabularies and data disclosure requirements. Pilot participants need to budget technical resource allocation and manage opportunity costs as developers may be redirected from other projects.

Figure 3: Email templates from the OAEBUDT DSaaS POC

Data Provider - step-by-step post credential sharing

Hi [TechnicalContactName]:

I wanted to confirm that you've received your data connector credentials [redacted] alongside the [detailed user guide](#) part of our growing [documentation](#) that walks through the step-by-step process to connect an endpoint or upload a file for the POC.

To test the POC, we would like each Data Provider to successfully connect and share an asset with a recipient(s) ASAP. We are very grateful that [OrgName] is willing to upload and test using a connector to get reports to [Partner DataRecipient OrgName].

At this stage, you should have everything you need to connect and configure your data connector:

1. Your COUNTER report for a given organization - this can be either the json SUSHI file or your own endpoint
2. Your Keycloak credentials to log in and obtain the time-sensitive access token to access the dataspace to configure your connectors. You should have access to [OrgName]'s sensitive Keycloak credential in which will allow you to [generate your temporary auth tokens](#)

Equipped with this information, you can connect a report for each recipient by taking three steps:

Step 1 - Authenticate in the Dataspace: Obtain your session auth token via Keycloak ([step-by-step](#)) which I believe is valid for one hour (after which you'd need to repeat this step to obtain a new token to use in the following steps.)

Step 2: Configure [OrgName]'s data recipients: Create two [OrgName] Partner Group's so you can provision a report to each organization via their group; one for each Data Recipient organization.

Participant DID (counterPartyId)	Domain (public)

- Tip: make sure you use your valid authorization token when you work through this step, or you will get an error.
- Tip: You can view a list of your successfully created groups when you're done. ([step-by-step](#))
- Tip: take care to not include < > or " " as you enter the information in Postman as including these characters at the ends of your text strings will result in errors

Step 3 - Create an asset (i.e. metadata) for each report so it is discovered by your intended data recipient. This is where you will describe the asset according to the OAEBUDT rulebook and set which partner can access it. ([step-by-step](#))

Once you complete these three steps, you will have created your federated catalog of [Org Name] assets in the OAEBUDT POC dataspace (i.e. the POC reports you'll be sharing with [Partner DataRecipient OrgName].) We will then be able to schedule a call with each of those partners independently to have them find, request, and call the data.

Data Recipient Step by Step post credential sharing

Hi [TechnicalContactName]:

I wanted to confirm that you've received your data connector credentials in Bitwarden alongside the [detailed user guide](#) and our growing [documentation](#) that walks through the step-by-step process to connect to access a data asset shared with you via the dataspace proof of concept.

[DataProviderOrgName] has already connected and shared an asset with you via the dataspace. Now you are able to generate a session token to pull down the data.

Note:

- In this POC, you'll manually work in an API via the command line or a GUI tool like [Postman](#), to replicate steps that will be automated in the full dataspace as machine to machine interactions.
- Tip: take care to not include < > or " " as you enter the information in Postman as including these characters at the ends of your text strings will result in errors.
- A push of the data is not supported in the POC, but is on our technical roadmap.
- If you have ideas as you pilot, please log any questions in our [discussions board](#) and feature requests or bugs in our [issues board](#).

Now you can authenticate in the POC and obtain the reports you have been granted access to by following 7 steps (most of which will be automated to scale in the full build.)

Step 1 - Authenticate in the Dataspace: Obtain your session auth token via Keycloak ([Step-by-Step](#)) which I believe is valid for [redacted] (after which you'd need to repeat this step to obtain a new token to use in the following steps.)

Step 2: Review the data asset(s) you have been granted access to: Find the asset you want to pull from the list of those that data providers have granted you access to through the dataspace's federated catalog ([Step-by-Step](#)).

Step 3: Identify the data asset to access in this session: You will need to capture four fields for the data asset of interest from your specific organization's federated catalog of data offerings. ([Step-by-Step](#))

Step 4: Obtain the ContractAgreement ID for this data asset exchange instance: by configuring and running the Machine to Machine (M2M) contract negotiation API ([Step-by-Step](#)) Once the contract is both requested and finalized, you will obtain a valid "Contract Agreement ID" which is auditable M2M signal that your connector has been granted access to the Data Provider's connector for the purposes of your express data exchange.

Step 5: Obtain your Transfer Process ID: by updating the template API with your ContractAgreementID ([Step-by-Step](#))

Step 6: Generate a Data Provider's Endpoint access token: by updating the template API with your TransferProcessID to obtain your data exchange session specific transfer access token ([Step-by-Step](#))

Step 7: Fetch the usage data asset report: by updating the template API with your Data Provider's public endpoint and your EDR access token. ([Step-by-Step](#))

—

As you are one of the first data recipients testing our documentation and minimum viable dataspace, we encourage you to try to do this on your own and reach out to the Think-IT team if you have questions. We are also happy to schedule a 30 minute call to support you as you go through the process. Please advise which path you'd like to follow.

We look forward to learning from your experience!

Participation Fee

If the infrastructure is not fully publicly subsidized, organizational data space participants pay to sustain central coordinating office administration and service provision. Legal review should be anticipated to review participation documents such as the DSaaS Participant Rulebook and related standard DSaaS participation agreement at time of onboarding and initial invoicing.

Outsourced Data Hosting or Data Connector as a Service

Subsidies or technical assistance grants may be necessary to ensure that less resourced organizations can access technical, cybersecurity, and data governance resources to directly connect into DSaaS workflows. Data processors or analytics firms supporting scholarly communications clients may futureproof brokerage or ingest dependent business models by preparing to offer such services to their clients.

Variance between Minimum Viable and Fully Operational Data Space Operational Costs

The initial development of the OAEBUDT DSaaS was advertised via a Request for Proposal (RFP)^{xlix} distributed via International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) and scholarly communications social media channels. Received proposals varied in cost but a \$40,000 development budget and one year timeframe necessitated developing a minimum viable proof of concept (POC) data space. The POC pilot aimed to explore the value and operational costs associated with data space operations. Baseline functionality was prioritized, while retaining extensibility for future development. Key data space functions moved out of the initial RFP to a technical roadmap for the scholarly communications data space include:

- web-interfaces for data providers, data recipients/consumers, and data space administration;
- transaction logging and report viewing capabilities enabled by a data space’s policy clearinghouse;
- integration of common verified identity solutions used in higher education and research institutions such as SAML via the InCommon Federation and Oauth; and,
- a marketplace where data recipients/consumers could search for and initiate access requests to controlled data connectors, allowing data to flow instantaneously if there was a policy match.

The cost of providing a DSaaS was modeled based on the minimum-viable POC infrastructure (Figure 3). Cloud computing costs associated with policy transaction clearing and data connector discovery will need to be incorporated into the cost model as costs become clear.

Figure 4: OAEBUDT Minimum Viable Proof of Concept Architecture^l

Ongoing Managed Data Space as a Service Costs

Outside of the R&D functions described above, a minimum amount is required to maintain the operational central infrastructure so that data connectors can function in a trusted data space environment. Costs can vary but must cover the provision of the following functions either internally or by a DSaaS provider:

- Organizational onboarding interface and verified identity provision
- Data connector discovery and configuration for data providers and data consumers
- Secrets management to ensure that sensitive data is not directly shared inappropriately without explicit policy approval as checked by the data connectors

In the OAEBUDT pilot, a flat monthly charge resulted from the provision of the identity and data connector service, alongside a “per-participant” amount to recover charges associated with the hosted data connector service. Contract negotiations for a future scholarly communications data space should ensure that both types of charges are clearly defined to inform pricing and flow-through charges.

As the DSaaS coordinating office matures and brings diverse revenue generation online, it will be better positioned to bring in-house human and technical resources to reduce dependencies and better control costs.

Data Space Cost Recovery

Funding is necessary for feature development and to subsidize the early stage of operations when the number of data space users (i.e. participants) is too small to cover the cost of cloud and coordination operations. Revenue generation options available to a DSaaS are dependent on the maturity of the infrastructure and its governance. With an operational Technical Readiness Level of 7 (TRL-7), not all options were available to the OAEBUDT-IDS during and immediately after the pilot. This section describes a range of cost recovery options in the order of feasibility given operational maturity.

Pre-Launch (<TRL 9) Options

Grant Awards for Research, Development, and Inclusive Engagement

Three-to-five-year grants can provide working capital for data space participant support and engagement, and technical research and development. However, substantial administrative and staffing overhead is required to apply for and administer such awards.ⁱⁱ

From 2022-2026, primary funding for the OAEBUDT effort was provided via a 1.29 million USD Mellon Foundation grant award to develop governance mechanisms for a data space focused on distributed usage data analytics. Additional funding from the US National Science Foundation supported open journal and open data supply chain and vocabulary mappingⁱⁱⁱ and a workshop related to national infrastructure for usage and impact reportingⁱⁱⁱⁱ.

Market shifts directly impacted public grant availability for global open infrastructure. The EU, Australian, and Canadian markets have publicly funded data space development, suggesting that a scholarly communications consortia based within this footprint is well positioned to seek public funding for data space development.

Supporter Contribution Campaigns

From 2024-2026 two campaigns raised unrestricted funds to sustain the DSaaS coordinating office. Both explained the viability of raising bridge funding and an operational reserve without dedicated development staff, while refining communications and administrative processes. Campaign participation opportunities were advertised to pilot

partners, Trustees, and the broader community via marketing channels while the DSaaS POC was under development.

Supporter Membership Pilot (Q4 2024-Q2 2025, 3 participants)

The “Supporter Membership” campaign aimed to determine whether currently engaged stakeholders could generate an operational reserve to launch operations as Mellon grant funding expired. Piloted administrative coordinating office workflows with the fiscal host. Trustees sought contributions, raising a sum of 30,000 Euro from Michigan Publishing, Project Muse and Johns Hopkins Press, and DE Gruyter’s eBound Foundation.

Founders Campaign (Q4 2025- Q1 2026, 1 participant)

Invest in Open Infrastructure consultants created campaign collateral using lessons learned from the prior campaign and stakeholder interviews. Value propositions and pitch decks were shared with potential contributors, resulting in a 10,000 Euro contribution made jointly by Johns Hopkins Press and Project Muse.

Campaign Pilot Findings

Across the two campaigns, coordinating office staff observed the following attributes that impacted cash flow and the data space participant experience:

- Long processing times were common as cross-border financial transactions involved research security and tax office reviews in support of vendor certification and payment, with tax and legal offices involved to generate non-standard tax forms and vendor set up for foreign payers/payees.
- “Supporter” and “member” terms had varied interpretations and implications across academic, commercial, and geographic boundaries, contributing to review and processing times.
- Unlike software licensing fees, the ability of organizations to pay “supporter membership” varied greatly; while membership model framing for open infrastructure support was familiar to library publishers and presses, it did not translate well to other types of data space participant organizations.

A federation of national data space networks may be preferred to a single global data space coordinating office, to streamline administrative processes and simplify regulatory compliance.

In-Kind Volunteer Effort

Some organizations wanted to contribute staff resources in-kind in lieu of financial contributions. However, volunteer management and coordination require staff capacity to ensure alignment with data space protocols and the DSaaS technical roadmap. While not feasible with minimal staffing, in-kind contributions may positively impact operations when the data space matures.

Debt or Venture Capital

Without raising working capital to cover cash flow and an operational reserve, the onboarding of participants for two-year terms was irresponsible when DSaaS operations could not be guaranteed per SLA terms of DSaaS participation. Like many innovative products and services both in and out of scholarly communications, the piloted technology entered the innovation “valley of death” ^{liv}, i.e. where good ideas fade because they lack funding support to transition from research to adoption. While debt or equity could support a commercial offering, a hosted not-for-profit program structure made it challenging to use such solutions to bridge funding gaps during the early stage of operations.

Annual Data Space Organizational Payment

The OAEBUDT Data Space Participant Rulebook requires payment by each data space participant to sustain coordination and remain “in good standing” as a member of the DSaaS network. A tiered pricing model with rates set by participant organization expenditures resulted from community consultation. The DSaaS modeled other open infrastructures that offer discounts to organizations in low- and medium- income countries. Consortia paying on behalf of multiple organizational participants would be eligible for a group discount given the consortia’s role in reducing fiscal administration and contract processing overhead. As network adoption grows, a not-for-profit data space coordinating office may reduce annual fees as centralized costs are spread across larger numbers of participants.

Membership-related fees face institutional scrutiny to ensure the cost benefits the institution. Service fees, by contrast, clearly express that a service is being received. While membership payment directly supports the collective governance of a DSaaS coordinating office, annual “service subscription” fees are common practice in SaaS and commonly found in public and private IT budgets. If the DSaaS supports diverse stakeholders across commercial enterprises, public institutions, higher education, and not-for-profit organizations, internal DSaaS subscription framing may simplify onboarding, payment authorization, and institutional review for participating data space organizations.

While the OAEBUDT rulebook and pilot used member/membership framing, a recommendation was made late 2025 to shift to participant/subscriber framing to support DSaaS participants.

Post Launch of DSaaS, Membership, and Participant-Governance

Conference Hosting

The coordinating office and organizational participants in a data space will require continual knowledge sharing and rulebook as additional data connectors arise. An annual event with paid registration could support such knowledge exchange while underwriting capacity for documentation, standards development, and governance.

Collective Open Infrastructure ‘Crowdfunding’

From 2023-2025, OAEBUDT investigated applying to SCOSS and the Open Book Collective, two collective funding programs for open scholarly infrastructures. Applications were not accepted due to the pre-launch, pilot status of OAEBUDT DSaaS operations (TRL-7), as both programs require operational status (TRL-9). (Table 5). Advertising the OAEBUDT DSaaS to support credibility via the open infrastructure focused InfraFinder was also not possible due to pre-launch status.

Table 6: Community Funding Opportunities for Operational Open Infrastructure

Organization	Funding Mechanism	Operational Requirement	Application Frequency	Potential Revenue Amount
Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS)	Global fundraising campaign support; 25k upfront program participation cost deducted from initial funds raised	Established service, operational for 2 years	Every 2 years	Unlimited; fundraising targets of past campaigns range 368,000-1.2M Euro
Open Book Collective	Discovery and payment handling service for supporter programs; participation fee 7.5%/5% funds raised in first/following years plus optional 5% of funds raised collective development fund fee	Operational service and membership program	Rolling	Unlimited; current offers range 60 - 4,600 Euro per year

Service Delivery Cost-Recovery

While fixed rate annual payments support the central coordination of data space community governance, pass-through charges for technical and customer support services beyond a threshold were deemed appropriate by community stakeholders. Passing on the direct charges resulting from on-demand support and varied cloud infrastructure needs can support diverse data space participants. Three types of optional services were identified that could be charged to participants to cost-recover expenses that exceed a threshold.

- Onboarding support: a one-time cost to recover staffing, customized communications or documentation, or travel support if open documentation and community resources are not sufficient.
- Hosted data connector: an on-going, variable cost tied to cloud computing charges resulting from how an organization's data connector is configured and how frequently it is used.
- Technical support: a variable cost to provide on-demand customer support to DSaaS participants that self-host their data connectors. Billing in blocks of support time is recommended to schedule and reserve capacity to meet SLAs and participant expectations.

The DSaaS budget model changes if such services are invoiced based on actual hours spent or fixed rates tied to a level of service. Cash flow, budgetary projections, and the ability to provide human resources in-house or through contract labor depends on the ability to project demand and pay for staff capacity at the time of need. Thus, fixed rates are recommended to facilitate cash flow management during the next phase of DSaaS development.

All service delivery would be subject to the appropriate Value-Added Tax (VAT) rate (21% for in 2025 in Belgium.) Such tax collection by the coordinating office host organization is required regardless of whether the service is provided by a commercial or not-for-profit entity. In a DSaaS, a decision must be made on whether to pass on the full 21% tax as a direct charge to DSaaS participants on top of the annual rate. Should the budget model absorb the tax cost for services, pricing should be adjusted since tax revenues are restricted to tax payment and not available for general operations.

In December 2025, OAEBUDT Membership and Sustainability Committee members unanimously supported direct service billing, noting that the "productization" of data space services can support the scaling of controlled data exchange for scholarly communications immediately with the usage data connector.

Comparative Analysis of Peer Infrastructures

In October 2023, publicly available webpages for ORCID, OA Switchboard, DOAJ, DOAB, OAPEN, Crossref, COUNTER, IRUS, OpenAIRE, and PKP were reviewed to inform membership model development. Membership and consortia tier pricing, associated charges, and benefits were shared with OAEBUDT governance for planning discussions.

At the time, some models, like OAPEN's, charged a flat annual organizational membership fee based on the country of legal incorporation, with higher fees for organizations based in wealthier countries. Other models, like ORCID, calculated rates differently on stakeholder type and revenue. DOAJ fees differed by stakeholder type, with fee schedules for academic and library organizations based on budget and for publishers set by number of titles in DOAJ. PKP institutional membership tiers were different for academic and library institutions (billed in small, medium, large, national tiers) and publisher and service providers where fees were based on revenue tiers. The separation of public and member benefits was examined for a subset of infrastructures to develop the initial framework for the OAEBUDT DSaaS.

Table 7: 2023 Member Benefit Analysis of Open Infrastructures

Benefit type category	Benefit Membership Restricted	ORCID	OA Switchboard	OPEN	Crossref	COUNTER	IRUS
Technical	Provide data	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Access trusted data / push updates	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Secure / Authenticated Sign-in	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Provide input on further development			X	X	X	X
Support	Technical Support	X		X			X
	One on one orientation / onboarding session	X		X			
Governance	Nominate a representative to stand for election to the Board	X			X	X	
	Vote in annual Board elections	X			X	X	
Community Engagement	Participate in member-only events (e.g., town hall meetings)	X		X		X	X
	Receive member newsletter and updates	X	X	X		X	X
Visibility	Acknowledgement of contributors on website		X	X		X	X
Benefit type category	Benefit Publicly Available and Freely Accessible						
Documentation	Access knowledge base, technical documentation	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Access use cases / best practices	X	X				X
	Access outreach / communications resources	X	X	X	X	X	X
Technical	Sandbox test environment access	X	X				
Community Engagement	Access to public events hosted by staff	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Participate in public events, working groups, committees	X	X	X	X		X

Stakeholder Feedback

Budget model and cost-recovery mechanisms were informed by stakeholder input from publishers, university presses, libraries, infrastructure and service providers, platforms, and standards effort representatives from across Europe, Northern America, Africa, and Oceania. Methodology was informed by research project PIs Drummond (UNT), Legré (OPERAS), and Tsiavos (OpenAIRE), the project’s Advisory Board^{iv}, the OAEBUDT’s Board of Trustees^{vi} and Membership and Sustainability Committee^{vii}. Iterative sessions obtained feedback on the data space’s revenue generation options and membership model.

Topic	Event	Date
Revenue generation mechanisms	Charleston Library Pre-Conference workshop	7 November 2023
	Researcher to Reader workshop	20-21 February 2024
Membership model	Virtual Focus Groups	20 March 2024
	OPERAS conference	24-26 April 2024

Revenue Generation Mechanisms

Feedback on the data space BMC and cost-recovery options was generated in workshops at the 2023 Charleston Library Conference and 2024 Researcher to Reader Conference.^{viii} Small group discussion explored how costs could be recovered in a sustainable way without reducing trust or impacting the neutrality of the data space. Feedback on the “pros or strengths” and “cons or weaknesses” of specific mechanisms was collected.

Over two thirds of participants supported annual organizational participant fees, grants, and service delivery cost recovery. The ability to maintain trust and neutrality with sponsors providing direct support was noted for further study, as sponsorship comfort varied depending on the source of funding, necessitating transparency, management of potential conflicts of interest, and restrictions on sponsor participation in governance.^{lix}

Membership Model and Benefits

In March 2024, an online focus group of six participants representing libraries, university presses, publishers, and service/platform providers provided feedback on the proposed data space governance structure and participant benefits. Over half of the participants supported limiting governance participation to members, with members publicly listed for transparency. The intent to be as open as possible, making resources available broadly surfaced regularly, with general events, mailing list and documentation published open access.^{lx}

Figure 5: Focus Group feedback shared with Membership and Sustainability Committee

What should be restricted to “Members” ?
What we heard...

What should be restricted to “Members” ?
What we heard... First

Membership Model Draft – April 2024

The OAEBUDT Board and Membership and Sustainability committee reviewed focus group feedback and the comparative analysis of peer infrastructures, to elect what benefits should be restricted to members of the OAEBUDT data space.^{lxi} The resulting membership and pricing model (Figure 5) was workshopped in an OPERAS conference session with 9 participants representing publishers, libraries, open infrastructure, platforms, and service providers based in Europe. Participants mostly supported the model; 86% agreed that tiered fees based on expenditure were reasonable. Comments signaled the need for inclusive pathways for engaging smaller organizations with limited resources. Term confusion over the distinctions between “organizational” and “supporting” members surfaced, as it was unclear whether an organization would need to join twice if they had both roles. Showing a lack of familiarity with data spaces, some questioned what data access would be provided at different levels, not realizing that data access was determined by data providers in line with pre-existing contractual agreements. Such comments indicated that data space awareness raising remained a priority to increase knowledge of how data sovereignty and data connectors in data spaces function differently than data commons or other centralized data repositories.

Late 2024, the Membership and Sustainability Committee revised the model to align with OPERAS’ fiscal host policies, making two key recommendations:

- Pricing of organizational DSaaS Organizational Membership fee tiers should vary based on organizational expenditures
- The “Supporting Member” naming convention should be depreciated as it was confusing and problematic for both the individuals or organizations seeking to provide financial support without participating in the data space as participants, i.e. Organizational Members. “Supporting Member” was confusing as it blended vocabularies of donations, gifts, and grantors (i.e., supporters) with annual membership.

Figure 6: April 2024 Draft OAEBUDT Membership Model

Second Membership Model Draft – February 2025

A revised membership model (Figure 7) was produced and presented for community consultation. Between February and March of 2025, 29 respondents provided feedback via an anonymous webform that was advertised via social media channels, e-newsletters, mailing lists and listservs. Responses reflected representatives of book content hosting platforms, publishers, aggregators, library, data processors, analytics services, and scholars from across Europe, North America, Australia, and Asia.

Overall feedback was supportive, yet respondents sought clarity on the value proposition of the data space and a usage data focused data connector service given existing COUNTER reporting workflows. Given comments on how annual expenditures would be determined, the model was refined further to note that tiered annual fees would be based on annual materials expenditures for libraries and annual expenditures for publishers, platforms and services. Affordability for smaller organizations was noted for continual observation post-launch, with subsidies likely required to support engagement.

Figure 7: Refined OAEBUDT DSaaS Membership Model

Governance Engagement

Concerns were raised over the time commitment required for “Organizational Member” participation in governance. Some respondents noted governance participation should be optional with nomination and voting privileges preferred to required attendance at an Assembly of the Commons or other governance meetings. Limiting sponsor engagement in governance to Trustee nomination was preferred by most respondents.

Annual Discounts

Consortia discounts on Organizational Membership were supported for groups of five or more joining together under a single entity that would administer payment and onboarding of the group, thereby reducing data space overhead. A multi-year prepayment discount was also supported to increase cash flow and support budgeting.

Supporter Transparency

“Supporter” replaced “Supporter Member” as the preferred term for entities wishing to contribute financially while not acting as a data space user, i.e. “Organizational Member”. Most respondents supported grouping public lists of supporters on the OAEBUDT data space website by level of contribution (e.g., bronze, silver, gold, diamond) to be transparent.

Budget Modeling

Stakeholder interviews and technical pilot outcomes surfaced variables that would impact costs, adoption rates, and revenue generation potential. After membership and governance models were developed, data space participant value propositions and post pilot cost and revenue models were created.

Pilot Findings for Development and Growth

Late 2025, consultants with Clarke & Esposito documented the experiences of five OAEBUDT DSaaS pilot participants in case studies.^{lxii} Interviews informed the development of a OAEBUDT Data Space Return on Investment Analysis^{lxiii} with multiple recommendations to inform the next stage of work, including the role of onboarding critical nodes and their partners to speed network adoption. Lowering the barrier of entry was noted as a precursor to broad engagement, underscoring the need to make it easy for organizations to financially and technically interconnect to the data space. Notably, the need to broaden the data space scope beyond OA book usage to other types of data sharing was determined to be key to the next phase.

Value Propositions

Consultants from Invest in Open Infrastructure interviewed key stakeholders to explore the potential value propositions tied to a broader data space effort for scholarly communications. High level value statements for library consortia, library publishers, commercial publishers, and platforms and services propositions were compiled and tested in fundraising campaigns.

Bridge Scenario Development

Diversifying operational funds from sole grant support to ongoing revenue generation requires staffing. Two- and three-year costs with low, medium, and high levels of staffing were created as “bridge-scenario” budgets for operational reserve planning. Each scenario budgeted two years of operation, with a 3% inflationary escalation and a year’s operational reserve calculated at the year two rate. These sums were aggregated to establish funding thresholds necessary to launch with bridge funding for two years (one year of operational cash flow plus one year of reserve) or three (two years of operational cash flow plus one year of operational reserve). A responsible operational launch was deemed possible once 66% of bridge scenario funds were secured.

To simplify planning by controlling variables, scenarios included rates based on continuing agreements with the OAEBUDT DSaaS pilot’s fiscal host and DSaaS provider.

Figure 8: Board Meeting Slide Introducing Early-Stage Cash-Flow Gap Impeding Launch

Figure 9: Board Meeting Slides Presenting Bridge Scenarios

The mid-range scenario (B3) was chosen as the target to plan towards to support launch success, continued awareness raising, and scalable growth recognizing that a critical mass was required to deliver DSaaS value. It included costs for 1.5FTE dedicated staff for the data space coordinating office, fractional or outsourced fiscal administration and outsourced data space provision, plus the development of key functionality to support adoption. Travel and conference registration support was also included in this budget given the need to raise awareness of data spaces across scholarly publishing stakeholders.

Revenue Modeling

A multi-modal revenue modeling worksheet was created; yet, it was too complex to inform how many members would be necessary to launch the sustainable service given the shifting economics facing scholarly publishing.

Figure 10: Revenue Modeling Worksheet

OAEBUDT Revenue Stream Modeling Worksheet
Change the shaded light grey cells to view how different membership and campaign targets generate projected revenues over 2 years

	# in 2025	2025 Rate	2025 Total	# in 2026	2026 Rate	2026 Total	2 Year Projection
Membership Dues - Single Year Commitments							
Member: Small< €500,000		€1,000	€0		€1,000	€0	
Member: Med €500,000 to €5,000,000		€2,500	€0		€2,500	€0	
Member: Medium Large€5,000,000 to €50,000,000		€5,000	€0		€5,000	€0	
Member: Large€50,000,000 to €100,000,000		€10,000	€0		€10,000	€0	
Member: Very Large> €100,000,000		€15,000	€0		€15,000	€0	
Total 1yr Term Membership Revenues			€0			€0	€0
Membership Dues - 2Year Upfront Payments							
Member: Small= €500,000		€1,800	€0		€1,800	€0	
Member: Med €500,000 to €5,000,000		€4,500	€0		€4,500	€0	
Member: Medium Large€5,000,000 to €50,000,000		€9,000	€0		€9,000	€0	
Member: Large€50,000,000 to €100,000,000		€18,000	€0		€18,000	€0	
Member: Very Large> €100,000,000		€27,000	€0		€27,000	€0	
Total 2yr Term Membership Revenues			€0			€0	€0
Membership Dues - 3Year Upfront Payments							
Member: Small= €500,000		€2,700	€0		€2,700	€0	
Member: Med €500,000 to €5,000,000		€6,750	€0		€6,750	€0	
Member: Medium Large€5,000,000 to €50,000,000		€13,500	€0		€13,500	€0	
Member: Large€50,000,000 to €100,000,000		€27,000	€0		€27,000	€0	
Member: Very Large> €100,000,000		€40,500	€0		€40,500	€0	
Total 3yr Term Membership Revenues			€0			€0	€0
Supporter Donations							
Founder Campaign Participant		€50,000	€0			€0	
Supporting Member Campaign Participants		€10,000	€0			€0	
Individual Gifts - 500		€500	€0			€0	
Individual Gifts - 100		€100	€0			€0	
Total Supporter Donations							€0
Consortial Membership Networks - 2Yr Upfront							
1000 member consortia		€2,250,000	€0			€0	
12 member consortia		€27,000	€0			€0	
5 member consortia		€11,250	€0			€0	
100 member consortia		€225,000	€0			€0	
Total 2Yr Term Consortial Membership Revenues							€0

A simpler single-revenue source model was favored in board discussions, namely the number of organizational payments that would be required to fund each bridge scenario at 50,000/organization or 10,000/organization levels. This provided targets for the Founding Supporter campaign.

Figure 11: Mid-Range Expense and Campaign Projections

OAEBUDT Scenario B3				3 year bridge		2 year bridge			
EXPENSES	Projected Y1 Total	Projected Y2 Total w/ 3% Escalation	Operational Reserve (Calc at Yr2 rates)	2 years of Operations plus 1Y Reserve	66% Goal of 2YOps & 1Y Reserve	1 year Operations & 1Y Reserve	66% Goal of 1Y Ops & 1Y Reserve	Amt raised	% of 2YB3 Target
Personnel								€250,000	14%
100% ED FTE fully loaded								€500,000	29%
50% CM FTE fully loaded								€750,000	43%
Subawards/Consultants/Subcontractors								€1,000,000	57%
Hosted IDS as a Service (Front-loaded to guarantee cash-flow to cover 4 self hosted, 16 DaaS IDS MVP users)	€116,420	€119,913	€119,913	€356,245		€236,333		€1,150,000	66%
IDS Full Build - Contracted Development	€350,000			€350,000		€350,000			
Fractional Administrative Support (12hrs/m)	€15,000	€15,450	€15,450	€45,900		€30,450			
Other									
Conference Travel	€15,000	€15,450	€15,450	€45,900		€30,450			
Conference Registrations	€10,000	€10,300	€10,300	€30,600		€20,300			
Total Direct Costs	€958,820	€627,085	€627,085	€2,212,989		€1,585,905			
Indirect Costs: fiscal sponsorship fee (10% DC)	€95,882	€62,708	€62,708	€221,299		€158,590			
Total Cost	€1,054,702	€689,793	€689,793	€2,434,288	€1,606,630	€1,744,495	€1,151,367		
Campaign targets									
# of organizations giving 50k to meet (one time cost of less than half an FTE)				49	32	35	23		
# of organizations giving 10k to meet				243	161	174	115		

Critical Mass to Breakeven with Flat Fee Model

Without publicly subsidized DSaaS infrastructure in place, commercial DSaaS estimates were used to establish a break-even point – i.e., the critical mass of participants required to sustain baseline data space operations, or in business parlance the number of users required to fully cost-recover costs associated with providing the service (i.e., COGS).

In 2025, stakeholder feedback shifted to reflecting that a fixed fee would be preferential to a multi-modal variable fee schedule based on service utilization. Thus, variable and fixed costs were entered into a COGS model to establish the point at which flat user fees (e.g., annual participant fee) could fully cost recover DSaaS service provision. This was illustrated graphically by the point where revenue generated exceeded total costs. The analysis shows how network adoption and scale enable sustainable DSaaS operations per this COGS analysis.

The importance of network adoption to launch became clear, as two-to-three dozen enterprises committing 50k or consortia representing 175 organizations contributing 10k each could provide cost recovery. Yet, cash flow remained a challenge to launching the DSaaS as cloud compute costs would be generated despite the number of participants onboarded.

Due to multiple factors, the financial goal to launch the MVP DSaaS with thin staffing and a year of operational reserve was not met. Thus, the OAEBUDT Board elected to pause operations while sunseting the OAEBUDT brand and governance body so that another broader coalition could emerge to carry the momentum forward. The OA Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT) Board of Trustees resolved to sunset the OAEBUDT brand and governance by April 30, 2026, provided notice to its fiscal host OPERAS-EU of this change, signaling willingness to support knowledge transfer to others willing to move this work ahead.

Figure 12: Breakeven Analysis at Flat 50k/org fee

Figure 13: Breakeven Analysis at Flat 10k/org fee

Next Steps

Based on the lessons learned between 2023 and 2025, the following path is recommended for those aiming to develop a broader scholarly communications data space.

Phase	Revenue Mechanism	Required for Action
1. Develop DSaaS Participant Network and Additional Data Connector Use Cases	Sponsorship, grant, conference revenue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Committed, strategically aligned lead organization with facilitation and administrative capacity
2. Secure bridge funding for operational launch and phase 2 DSaaS development	Grant, Loan, Venture Capital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Committed Network of enterprises ready to migrate to DSaaS Coordinating office fiscal administration host selected, staffed
3. Launch DSaaS Participant membership and/or subscription model	Annual, recurring participant payments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Governance documentation and processes Initial participant network size to cover costs directly or secured sponsor subsidy
4. Launch DSaaS Service Delivery Direct or in Partnership	Service delivery and/or % overhead on pass-thru service revenue to cost-recover coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DSaaS Participant base Service delivery capacity within Coordinating Office, fiscal host, or partner vendors
5. Join open infrastructure support programs (e.g., OBC, SCOSS)	Structured monthly/annual payment resulting from crowdfunding, Campaign Advertising	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1-2 years of operational status

Develop DSaaS Participant Network and Additional Data Connector Use Cases

Consortia and other trade associations providing centralized services to organizational members are well positioned to explore launching a broader DSaaS to provide valuable sensitive data connectors across their stakeholders. Potential hosts could include infrastructure consortia, national research and education networks, library consortia, or publishing trade organizations. Webinars hosted mid-2026 by WDS, SSP and BISG for repositories, scholarly publishers, and book publishers started to surface potential use cases for additional data connectors.

Secure Funding for Additional Data Space Development and Launch

Once critical nodes and networks of DSaaS adopters have defined the mission-critical data connectors they are willing to adopt, funding should be secured to develop these, leveraging the open source DSaaS and usage data connector work. Once a data space is brought online, the usage data connector service can be refined and deployed.

Launch Organizational Membership and Governance

Once a network of organizational participants large enough to fiscally sustain operations is committed, participant-led governance bodies can form, with care taken to reduce the administrative and governance time required for organizational participation. Sponsors of the data space at that time should be engaged in the nomination process per feedback noted above.

Host or Partner to provide Data Space as a Service Delivery

Depending on the needs and technical capacity of the data space network of organizations, governance must decide whether to self-host or outsource cloud computing and DSaaS maintenance. The provision of data connectors for lesser resourced organizations and technical support for onboarding participants must be planned for. Additional revenues may be generated at this time through on-demand support services.

Join Open Infrastructure Programs

As noted above, collective funding opportunities for open infrastructures can generate unrestricted funds, however they require operational data space status. Once the DSaaS is operational with an initial network of organizations, such funding can support further growth, research, and development.

Infrastructure Maturity Assessment

As data spaces develop to serve interconnected global data supply chains, self-assessment tools can guide DSaaS development through comparative models informed by peer efforts.

Data Space Maturity Model

Developed and maintained by the Data Space Support Centre, the Data Space Maturity Model covers technical, governance, and community development operations. The self-assessment questionnaire allows data space efforts to examine and score their development against other known data spaces. This tool was used at the end of the OAEBUDT DSaaS pilot. Scores reflected were lower due to the late 2025 mission shift from OA book usage to scholarly communications more broadly; governance and sustainability resources from the OAEBUDT DSaaS pilot will need to be revised accordingly.

Principles of Open Infrastructure Model

Many scholarly communications stakeholders perceive sustainability to be entwined with openness to prevent vendor lock-in. The POSI self-evaluation framework guides the assessment of progress towards becoming a self-sustaining, reliable open infrastructure.

Conclusion

At the end of 2025, the minimum-viable OAEBUDT DSaaS system was successfully piloted with a usage data connector. Yet, stakeholder feedback reflected that data space value in scholarly communications is generated when multiple types of sensitive data can be aggregated, benchmarked, or made accessible to AI, beyond the scope of open access, the humanities, book publishing, or book usage.

This document aims to inform those who will carry forward the development of scholarly communications data spaces.

The opportunity now exists for leading scholarly communications organizations to advance this work with a broader mission to support multiple types of sensitive data connections for contextual analytics and AI.

Endnotes

- ⁱ Brian O'Leary, & Kevin Hawkins. (2019). Exploring Open Access Ebook Usage. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.17613/8rty-5628>
- ⁱⁱ Learn more about International Data Spaces at: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/why/data-spaces/>
- ⁱⁱⁱ Learn more about International Data Spaces at: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/why/data-spaces/>
- ^{iv} <https://www.gida-global.org/care>
- ^v Nagel, L., & Lycklama, D. (2021). Design Principles for Data Spaces - Position Paper (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105744>
- ^{vi} <https://www.iso.org/standard/86589.html>
- ^{vii} <https://www.iso.org/standard/93502.html> based on prior version available at: <https://eclipse-dataspace-protocol-base.github.io/DataspaceProtocol/2025-1-RC4/>
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^{xxvii} <https://github.com/OAEBUDT/oaebudt-dataspace/wiki>

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^{xxxi} <https://www.deltathink.com/news-views-market-sizing-update-2024-has-oa-hit-a-peak>

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^{xxxviii} https://github.com/International-Data-Spaces-Association/IDS-RAM_4_0

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^{xl} <https://github.com/OAEBUDT/oaebudt-dataspace>

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^{xlii} For details about the pilot see: Ricci, L., & Clarke, M. (2025). OAEBUDT Return on Investment Case Study Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17860210>

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^{xliv} See the OAEBUDT technical roadmap compiled at the end of the end of proof-of-concept development at <https://github.com/orgs/OAEBUDT/projects/4>

^{xlv} Sensors 2023, 23(9), 4315; <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23094315>

^{xlvi} Both an RFP process and a closed interview process were used to identify the fiscal host of the OAEBUDT coordinating office. Issues raised during the evaluation process included potential conflicts of interest and reputation as a trusted, neutral partner across stakeholder groups and geographies. Given market distinctions and geopolitics, such issues may suggest a federated network of data spaces could more effectively navigate these issues of trust in a coordinating office host organization.

^{xlvii} For more information on Technical Readiness Levels, see <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/career-development/researchers/manual-scientific-entrepreneurship/major-steps/trl>

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ⁱ Source: <https://github.com/OAEBUDT/oaebudt-dataspace/blob/main/docs/PoC-Proposal-architecture.png>

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ⁱⁱⁱ See project outputs in <https://zenodo.org/communities/securerimsupplychainandvocabulary/records?>

ⁱⁱⁱⁱ Workshop agenda and report are available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/2023-workshop-exploring-national-infrastructure-for-public-access-usage-and-impact-reporting/records>

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^{lv} List of advisory board members <https://www.oabookusage.org/2022forward>

^{lvi} List of Trustees available at: <https://www.oabookusage.org/governance>

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^{lix} Workshop data and coding was included in the dataset of sustainability consultation responses across four worksheets: “Charleston2023_Ideation”, “Charleston2023_MentiResults”, “R2R2024_Ideation”, and “R2R2024_MentiResults”. which is published in Zenodo at:

^{lx} See Rabar, U., & Drummond, C. (2024). Sustainable Open Infrastructure Cost Recovery Workshop Outputs [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13851626> “FG and Governance Responses” columns D:E.

^{lxi} Outputs: Collected information was appended to the dataset of sustainability consultation responses, in the worksheet “FG and Governance Responses” in columns J:O and published to Zenodo

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